

**ANTIPYRETIC EFFECTS OF EXTRACTS AND SOLVENT FRACTIONS FROM
TRICLISIA GILLETII (DE WILD) STANER (MENISPEMACEAE) ROOT BARK
TOWARDS BREWER'S YEAST INDUCED PYREXIA IN SWISS ALBINO MICE**

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ABSTRACT

The present study to the investigation of aqueous and its solvent fractions as well as methanol 80% from *Triclisia gilletii* root barks by using the toxic Brewer's yeast induced high rectal temperatures in Swiss albino mice was conducted. The difference between 0 hour and respective time intervals of recorded temperatures compared to toxic negative control Brewer's yeast group was performed. Results revealed that the subcutaneous injection of the toxic Brewer's yeast induced high rectal temperatures from 39.9±0.09 to 40.3±0.5°C in 1 and after 5h of administration the toxic. Next, the oral administration of Aspirin as reference antipyretic drug at dose of 100 mg/kg bodyweight in mice with pyrexia reached significant lowering of rectal temperatures from 37.5±0.2 to 34.6±0.8 after 1 and 5h of treatment. In the same manner, the oral administration of aqueous and methanol 80% extracts at high dose of 400 mg/kg bodyweight caused remarkably decrease of rectal temperature to values of 38.0±0.6 and 37.5±0.5°C in 1h of treatment and continued to land until to 37.0±0.4 and 36.5±0.5°C after 5h of treatment. Moreover, the oral administration of chloroform, ethylacetate, *n*-butanol and residual aqueous solvent fractions at the same oral dose reached also significant lowering of rectal temperatures from 37.3±0.5 to 39.0±0.6°C and from 37.0±0.5 to 36.7±0.5 after 1 and 5h of treatment respectively while crude polysaccharides acted the same manner by producing significant reduction of rectal temperatures from 38.7±0.7 to 36.5±0.8°C after the same times of treatment. In definitive, these significant lowering of rectal temperatures in treated mice with pyrexia compared to toxic Brewer's yeast clearly demonstrated that these samples from *Triclisia gilletii* root bark were endowed with good and interesting antipyretic effects in animal model.

KEYWORDS: *Triclisia gilletii*, Menispermaceae, root barks, extracts, solvent fractions, crude polysaccharide, antipyretic activity.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fever is a common medical sign once the human's body temperature goes above the normal range (36.5–37.5°C) secondary to infections, tissue damages, inflammations, malignancy, graft rejections, and other inflammatory

disease conditions (Dalal et al., 2006, Sullivan et al., 2011, Yimer et al., 2021). It is also an important and notable sign symptom of many diseases that are caused in the human body. They are the result of any inflammatory condition, infections or any other diseases

occurring due to any external agents. When a person's body temperature rises above the normal range (36.5–37.5°C) due to an infection, tissue damage, malignancy, transplant rejection or other inflammatory disease conditions, they are said to have a fever. Up to 75% of extremely sick patients experience fever or pyrexia (Ogoina et al., 2011, Jyothi et al., 2024).

Fever is the body's natural defense to create an environment where an infectious agent or damaged tissue cannot survive since many of the microbial agents that cause infection grow supreme at normal body temperatures and their growth is inhibited by temperatures in the fever ranges (Dalal et al., 2006, Yimer et al., 2021). Thus, a lack of fever may contribute to lower resistance to infection, delayed recovery, and suboptimal outcome. Lower febrile responses to infection are associated with a higher mortality rate and poor prognosis of any human disorders (Ogoina et al., 2011, Yimer et al., 2021, Jyothi et al., 2024) et al., 2024).

Fever can occur for a variety of reasons but are often the result of a virus like a cold or flu. There are several things you can try to reduce your fever and relieve any other common symptoms. One category of these options is home remedies, such as ones that help to physically cool your body and bring your temperature down based on your external environment. Another category is over-the-counter medicines that can work by combatting fever-causing mechanisms in your body. It may also be beneficial to combine physical interventions with drugs that can help to break your fever (Anonymous, 2025).

This natural response creates an environment conducive to the body's defense mechanisms, aiding in tissue repair and rendering it inhospitable for infectious agents. Infected or damaged tissue produces different inflammatory mediators such as Interleukin (IL-1 β), Interferon (IFN- α and β) (Yimer et al., 2021). This natural response creates an environment conducive to the body's defense mechanisms, aiding in tissue repair and rendering it inhospitable for infectious agents. Infected or damaged tissue produces different inflammatory mediators such as Interleukin (IL-1 β), Interferon (IFN- α and β) Tumor Necrosis Factor (TNF- α), thereby increasing the synthesis of Prostaglandin E (PGE-2) in the hypothalamus (Rakib et al., 2020).

Additionally, PGE-2 binds to the PGE-2 type 3 receptor on glial cells, leading to the generation and release of cyclic Adenosine Monophosphate (cAMP). This serves as a neurotransmitter and simultaneously triggers thermosensitive neurons, elevating the thermostatic set point from normothermic levels to induce fever (Nhung et al., 2023). Subsequently, when having a fever, sufferers often feel discomfort such as pains (myalgia), chills, anorexia, inability to concentrate, increased muscle tone and lethargy (Ames et al., 2017), thereby drugs are needed in order to reduce fever and its effects (Alkandahri et al. 2022).

Presently, nearly all antipyretic medications, including Non-Steroidal Anti-Inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs), function by inhibiting the synthesis of PGE-2 through irreversible blocking of the Cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) enzyme with high selectivity and (Gunarti et al., 2025) lower fever. Currently available antipyretic nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) have been linked to gastrointestinal side effects, renal and liver dysfunction, and a slew of other problems (Aronof et al., 2001). Selective-cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) inhibitors like Celecoxib, Valdecoxib, and Rofecoxib, can alleviate gastrointestinal side effects to some extents, however, these agents are toxic to hepatic cells, glomeruli, the cortex of the brain and the heart muscles. Other antipyretic drugs include Paracetamol or Divalgan, Aspirin, Novalgine, Ibuprofen, Naproxen, etc. currently used by people having function of fever Reduction: They treat elevated body temperature (pyrexia) and symptom Relief: Relieve headache, muscle aches, and chills associated with fever. They have as mechanism of action the blocking cyclooxygenase, inhibiting the production of prostaglandin E_2 (PGE $_2$) in the brain, which in turn acts on the hypothalamus to lower the raised thermoregulatory setpoint (Anonymous, 2025).

As a result, research into the discovery of new antipyretic agents that are safe, more effective, and less expensive, particularly from natural products, is encouraged (Aronof et al., 201, Sun et al., 2007, Alves, 2023, Tegegne and Alehegn, 2023). A large portion of the global healthcare industry is comprised of medicinal plants and herbal treatments. At least 80% of people now rely on herbal remedies and dietary supplements in some capacity for their basic healthcare, a dramatic growth in usage over the previous three decades (Ekor, 2014).

When a person's body temperature rises above the normal range (36.5–37.5°C) due to an infection, tissue damage, malignancy, transplant rejection, or other inflammatory disease conditions, they are said to have a fever (Walter et al., 2016, Tegegne et al., 2023). Up to 75% of extremely sick patients experience fever or pyrexia. It occurs in 19 to 30% of pediatric emergency visits, which creates tension among parents (Sullivan et al., 2011, Tegegne et al., 2023). A fever occurs because your body trying to fight with viruses or bacteria, that cause the infection. The sign and symptoms of fever are chills and shivering, headache, sweating, muscle aches, dehydration, general weakness. For management of fever various systems of medicines are currently used (Nilima et al., 2021).

The pyrogenic exogenous and endogenous substances are necessary for the initiation, manifestation, and management of the febrile reaction. Exogenous pyrogens, including interleukin-1b, enhance the creation and release of internal pyrogens, which causes it (IL-1b). On the other hand, endogenous pyrogens relocate to the hypothalamic organum vasculosum of the lamina terminalis (OVLT), where they induce the production of

prostaglandins E2 (PGE2). Due to this, the thermostatic set-point rises, which results in a feverish reaction (Ogonia et al., 2011, El-Radhi, 2019, Tegegne et al., 2023, Jyothi et al., 2024).

Pyrexia or Fever is defined as an elevation of body temperature or Pyrexia (fever) refers to an elevation in the body temperature beyond the homeostatic level as a result of stressful conditions such as ovulation, elevated thyroid hormone secretion, tedious exercise, lesion of the central nervous system (CNS) and infectious agents. It is a response due to tissue damages, inflammations, malignancy or graft rejection (Rajani et al., 2011, Kavitha et al., 2018). Fever is associated with symptoms of sickness behaviour which consist of lethargy, depression, anorexia, sleepiness inability to concentrate.

Antipyretic medication can be effective at lowering the temperature which may include the affected people's comfort (Duraisankar et al., 2012, Kavitha et al., 2018). Plants have been a major source for new drug design. In ethnobotany, plants with naturally occurring antipyretic activity are commonly referred as febrifuge agents (Kavitha et al., 2018).

Pyrexia or fever is the increase in body temperature above normal physiological ranges 36.5-37.5°C, which may result due to physiological stress such as during microbial infections as natural defense system of the body is activated.^[32] Usually, at the elevated body temperature, there is increased production of proinflammatory mediators' cytokines such as interleukin 1 β , β , α and TNF- α which enhance the formation of prostaglandin E2 (PGE2) near the peptic hypothalamus area and the prostaglandin in turn act on the hypothalamus. It refers to an elevation in the body temperature beyond the homeostatic level as a result of stressful conditions such as ovulation, elevated thyroid hormone secretion, tedious exercise, lesion of the central nervous system (CNS) and infectious agents (Sultana et al., 2015).

Pyrexia is not a disease but is a sign of numerous diseases usually caused by various bacteria and viruses (Ahmad et al., 2014, 2018). Pyrexia, commonly known as fever, is an elevation of body temperature above the normal range, typically defined as 38.0°C (100.4°F) or higher, caused by the hypothalamus raising the body's temperature set-point. It acts as a defense mechanism against infections, often causing symptoms like chills, shivering, sweating, headaches, and fatigue. Fever or pyrexia in humans is a symptom of an anti-infection defense mechanism that appears with body temperatures exceeding the normal ranges caused by an increase in the body's temperatures set-point in the hypothalamus (Garmel, Mahadevan 2012, Dinarello and Porat, 2018, Franjić, 2019). There is no single agreed-upon upper limit for normal temperature: sources use values ranging between 37.2 and 38.3 °C (99.0 and

100.9 °F) in humans (Laupland, 2009, Dinello and Porat, 2018).

Treat fever with rest, increased fluid intake (water, broth) to prevent dehydration, and over-the-counter medication like paracetamol (acetaminophen) or ibuprofen. Keep the room temperature comfortable, wear light clothing, and use a cool, damp cloth for comfort. Seek medical advice if fever exceeds 103°F (39.4°C), lasts over three days, or is accompanied by severe symptoms. For the treatment of fever, fever treatment focuses on relieving discomfort rather than eliminating the fever itself, as it is a natural defense against infections. Key measures include staying hydrated with water or fluids, getting ample rest, and using OTC (Over-The-Counter) medications like Paracetamol or Daphalgan (acetaminophen), Ibuprofen, Aspirin, Novalgine, etc. to manage discomfort. Most fevers, which often last 3 to 4 days, do not require medical intervention unless they are exceptionally high or persistent. Their key treatment strategies include medication: take Paracetamol or Ibuprofen to lower temperature and reduce pains, but avoid alternating them to prevent dosage errors, hydration: drink plenty of fluids to prevent dehydration, which is critical as the body burns more energy during a fever, comfort measures: wear light clothing, keep the room temperature comfortable, and use light bedding, cooling methods: apply a cool, wet washcloth to the forehead, neck, or wrists and avoid: do not take cold baths or showers, as shivering can raise body temperature. Never give aspirin to children. Up to 102 F (38.9 C) taken rectally for children ages 2-3, or taken orally for children older than 3 (Staff, 2025),

When to seek medical attention: Call a healthcare provider if the fever persists for more than 3 days, or if it is accompanied by symptoms such as a severe headache, stiff neck, shortness of breath, or rash. For adults, a fever of 103°F (39.4°C) or higher usually requires attention.

Common Causes: Fevers are commonly caused by viral or bacterial infections, such as the flu, cold, COVID-19, or other illnesses. Prevention: preventing fevers involves reducing exposure to infections, which includes frequent handwashing, staying away from sick individuals, and staying home while contagious. Fever is most commonly caused by infections-viral (e.g., flu, COVID-19, colds) or bacterial (e.g., UTIs (Urinary Tract Infections), pneumonia, strep throat)-as the immune system raises body temperature to combat pathogens. Other frequent causes include inflammatory conditions (arthritis), reactions to medications or vaccinations, heat exhaustion, and underlying chronic illnesses like cancer. Fevers are commonly caused by viral or bacterial infections, such as the flu, cold, COVID-19, or other illnesses. (Anonymous, 2025a).

Fever treatment focuses on relieving discomfort rather than eliminating the fever itself, as it is a natural defense against infection. Key measures include staying hydrated

with water or fluids, getting ample rest, and using OTC medications like Paracetamol (acetaminophen), Ibuprofen and others to manage discomfort. Most fevers, which often last 3 to 4 days, do not require medical intervention unless they are exceptionally high or persistent.

They key treatment strategies included

- Medication: Take paracetamol or ibuprofen to lower temperature and reduce pain, but avoid alternating them to prevent dosage errors.
- Hydration: Drink plenty of fluids to prevent dehydration, which is critical as the body burns more energy during a fever.
- Comfort Measures: Wear light clothing, keep the room temperature comfortable, and use light bedding.
- Cooling Methods: Apply a cool, wet washcloth to the forehead, neck, or wrists.
- Avoid: Do not take cold baths or showers, as shivering can raise body temperature. Never give Aspirin to children.

When to seek medical attention: Call a healthcare provider if the fever persists for more than 3 days, or if it

is accompanied by symptoms such as a severe headache, stiff neck, shortness of breath, or rash. For adults, a fever of 103°F (39.4°C) or higher usually requires attention.

Prevention: Preventing fevers involves reducing exposure to infections, which includes frequent handwashing, staying away from sick individuals, and staying home while contagious (Anonymous, 2025a).

2. MATERIELES AND METHODS

2.1. Vegetal material

Fresh roots of *Triclisia gillettii* were collected in Kinzaweta collectivity in Bas-Congo (Democratic Republic of Congo). The plant was identified at Institut National d'Etudes et de Recherches en Agronomie (INERA), Faculty of Sciences and Technologies, Department of Biology, University of Kinshasa/Kinshasa where a voucher specimen No Tgrb12480 was been deposited in the herbarium of this institute. Fresh *Triclisia gillettii* root bark were dried at normal temperature for three days, cuted in small pieces and reduced to powder using an traditional mortal resulting in a powder kept in a brun bottle before use to avoid contamination.

Figure 1: *Triclisia gillettii* leaves and twigs.

2.2. Preparation of extracts and frationation of extracts

50g of root bark powder were mixed with 300 mL distilled water and heated on hot plaque at 100°C for 15 minutes. After cooling and filtration on sterile cotton and paper filter Whatman N° 1, the resulting filtrate was evaporated in rotative evaporator giving dried extract of 22.13 g denoted as Tgrb-1.

On the other hand, 20 g of plant material was mixed with 200 mL methanol 80% and macerated for 24h. After filtration in the same conditions described above, a macerate was obtained. The marck was exhaustively percolated with the same solvent and filtered in the same conditions as described above. The macerate and percolate were combined and evapored in *vacuo* giving a dried extract denoted as Tgrb-2 (12.67 g).

Next, an amount of each extract Tgrb-1 and 2 (10 g) was dissolved in 200 mL distilled water and treated as

described above. The resulting filtrates were separately, exhaustively and successively extracted with solvents of different polarities like chloroform, ethylacetate and *n*-butanol. All fractions including residual aqueous fraction was treated as described above giving corresponding dried extracts denoted as Tgrb-1.1.1 (1.25 g), Tgrb-1.1.2 (2.65 g), Tgrb-1.1.3 (1.52 g) and Tgrb-1.1.4 (3.25 g) and Tgrb-1.2.1 (1.54g) Tgrb-1.2.2 (2.71 g), Tgrb-1.2.3 (1.72 g) and Tgrb-1.2.4 (3.45 g) for chloroform, ethylacetate, *n*-butanol and residual aqueous fractions from aqueous extract Tgrb-1 and methanol 80% Tgrb-2 extract respectively (Tgrb: *Triclisia gillettii* root bark).

2.3. Chemical screening

The confirmatory qualitative phytochemical screening of plant extracts was performed to identify the main classes of compounds (alkaloids, tannins, saponins, flavonoids, coumarins, polyphenols, glycosides, polysachharides, reductor sugars, steroids, and terpenoids) in the extracts following standard protocols.

Test for Tannins

About 2 mg of the plant extract was dissolved in 5 mL distilled water and 1 mL Stiasny reagent (formol + HCl conc.) was added to the mixture giving a brun precipitate for catechin tannins as positive test. The mixture was filtered on paper filter Whatman n° 1 and in the filtrate, 1 mL FeCl₃ 5% was added giving grey color for gallic tannins as positive test.

Test for Alkaloids

The plant extract was dissolved in 5 mL of water, filtered, and Then, 1 mL of the heated mixture was combined with 1 mL of Mayer-Wagner reagent or Dragendorff reagents giving white yellowish and orange precipitate respectively as positive tests.

Test for Saponins

About 0.5 milliliters of the extract and 5 mL of distilled water were combined and vigorously agitated. Then, the formation of foam persisting during 10 minutes confirmed the presence of saponins.

Test for Flavonoids and Glycosides

200 mg of the plant extract was mixed with 10 mL of ethanol and filtrated. Two mL of the filtrate, concentrated HCl, and magnesium ribbon (Shinoda reagent) were mixed. The formation of a pink or red color indicates the presence glycosides or flavonoids. After, adding 1 mL of distilled water and NaOH to 1 mL solution of extract, the formation of a yellowish color indicated the presence of flavonoids.

Test for Steroids

About 1 mL of the crude extract was combined with 10 mL of chloroform and 10 mL of sulfuric acid conc. (Liebermann-Burchard reagent), and the formation of the bilayer (red top layer and greenish bottom layer) reveals the presence of steroids.

Test for Terpenoids

The presence of terpenoids was determined by the formation of a reddish-brown color in the test for terpenoids, which included mixing of 0.5 mL of crude extract with 2 mL of chloroform and 3 mL of sulfuric acid conc. (Liebermann-Burchard reagent) or Salkowski reagent (0.5 M ferric chloride (FeCl₃) in 35% perchloric acid (HClO₄) water and H₂SO₄ concentrated giving pink or red color as positive test.

Test for Phenols

About 1 mL of the extract was combined with three drops of FeCl₃ 5%, and 1 mL of K₂Fe (CN)₆ (Barton reagent). The formation of brune precipitate and blue color respectively confirmed the presence of phenols.

Test for polysaccharides

To 1 mL solution of extract, formol + H₂SO₄ conc. was added giving various colors as positive test.

Reductor sugars

To 1 mL solution of extract, 1M Fehling reagent composed of two separate solutions, Fehling A (blue) and Fehling B (colorless), mixed just before use, Fehling A contains aqueous copper(II) sulfate, while Fehling B contains potassium sodium tartrate (Rochelle salt) and sodium hydroxide in water, forming a blue tartrate-complex of Cu(II) that acts as an oxidizing agent in an alkaline environment to detect reducing sugars, was added, mixed and boiled giving a red color as positive test.

Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) Test

Thin layer chromatography was performed on TLC plate (silica gel pre-coated with layer thickness of 0.2 mm, Merck, Germany) to confirm the presence of some phytochemical using hexane/ethyl acetate 8:2 as mobile phase for steroids and terpenoids using Liebermann-Bouchardat as reagent, BAW 4:1:5 (top layer) for flavonoids using AlCl₃ reagent, CHCl₃/MeOH/NH₃ 10:9:1 for alkaloids using Dragendorff reagent and Coumarin under UV using NaOH. Spots were applied using capillary tube 1.5 cm from the bottom marked by a line ruled using a pin. The sample spotted on the plate was allowed to dry before the plate was placed into the chromatographic tank which was covered immediately. When the solvent reaches the top of the plate, the plate was removed, marked and dried. The number of the spots was detected under UV at 254 and 366 nm wavelengths and spraying with appropriate reagent (Harborne, 1998, Trease and Evans, 2000).

2.5. Evaluation of antipyretic activity**2.5.1. Induction of fever or pyrexia**

Antipyretic activity was evaluated using methods previously described by Tesema and Makonnen., 2015, Olorukooba et al., 2020 and Tegegne et al., 2023). The normal body temperature of each mice was checked by using digital thermometer at the beginning of the study. Pyrexia was induced in all mice by subcutaneous injecting a 30% w/v Brewer's yeast suspension in 0.9% normal saline (*Sacchromyces cervisiae*) at a dose of 10 mL/kg bw below the nape of the neck. Animals were fasted with free access to only water *ad libitum*, after injection of the toxicant Brewer's yeast after 5h. Rectal temperature of each selected mice was then recorded and pyrexia was confirmed by increase in temperatures between 38 and 40.3°C and these mice were selected for the experiment, while animals showing less than 1°C rise in temperature were excluded.

2.5.2. Treatment of Swiss albino mice with fever or pyrexia

The selected mice subcutaneously injected with the toxicant Brewer's yeast at dose of 10 mL/kg bw were randomly divided in following groups of 3 mice each:

- Group I was orally administered 5 mL distilled water as test normal negative control,
- Group II received 5 mL distilled water and the toxicant Brewer's yeast suspension by subcutaneous injection of 10 mL/kg bw corresponding to 3g/kg bw

of 30% w/v Brewer's yeast to induce pyrexia or fever state as test toxic negative control,

- Group III received orally Aspirin at oral of 100 mg/kg bw as positive control,
- Groups IV and Va and b were separately and orally administered 200 (a) and 400 (b) mg/kg bw of aqueous Mms-1 and methanol Mms-2 extract respectively.
- Group VI to IX were separately and orally administered the same doses with chloroform, ethylacetate, *n*-butanol and residual aqueous Tgrb-1.1.1 to 1.1.4 and Tgrb-1.2.1 to 1.2.4 solvent fractions respectively.

The experiment used only mice that showed a temperature increase of $\geq 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ and received the toxican Brewer's yeast injection. One hour after the yeast administration of all samples, the rectal temperature of each mice had been measured again to coincide with the stable or peak phase of fever indicating an appropriate time to test the antipyretic activity of test samples. The rectal temperature of all groups was recorded at 1, 3 and 5h.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Medicinal plant extracts exhibited significant antipyretic activity by reducing fever, often comparable to conventional drugs like aspirin, by inhibiting prostaglandin E₂ (PGE₂) synthesis in the hypothalamus. Key compounds like flavonoids and terpenoids in plants such as *Eucalyptus globulus*, *Senna didymobotrya*, and *Leucas aspera* modulate the pre-optic area of the hypothalamus to lower elevated body temperature (Mworja et al., 2019).

The hypothalamus regulated body temperature by maintaining a balance between heat production and heat loss through set-point control. However, under the conditions such as infections, tissue damages, inflammations and various health issues, an elevated or enhanced set-point may occur (Franco-Trepas et al., 2022). During the increase of set-point, there was an increase in body temperature through active generation and retention of heat while vasoconstriction also played a role in helping reduce heat loss through skin. In this way, the body matches the brain's blood temperature with the new set-point created by hypothalamus (Zeng et al., 2022, Gunarti et al., 2025).

Anti-pyretic drugs inhibit the expression of COX-2, leading to the reduction in the PGE₂ biosynthesis, which is the major fever mediator (MurakaMi et al., 2011, Mworja et al., 2019) Anti-pyretic drugs have an inhibitory activity on prostaglandin biosynthesis but do influence body temperature if the elevation is caused by an increase in ambient body temperature or body exercise.^[6] Other therapeutic agents employed in the treatment of pyrexia include steroids and opioids among others. Fever is managed using antipyretic agents such as

Diclofenac, Ibuprofen, Aspirin and Paracetamol, etc. (Mworja et al., 2019).

The inflammatory cascade is classically characterized by pyrexia, oedema, hyperaemia, and nociception (Nwaehujor et al., 2015). Within traditional medicine practice, botanicals and phytochemicals are harnessed for the management of various ailments, particularly those associated with pyrexia, nociception and inflammation. Several studies have elucidated that the anti-inflammatory and analgesic efficacies of herbal extracts and phytochemicals primarily stem from their modulation of arachidonic acid (AA) metabolism, cyclooxygenase (COX), lipoxygenase (LOX), pro-inflammatory cytokines, inducible nitric oxide, and nuclear factor kappa B (NF- κ B) transcriptional activation (Nworu and Akah, 2015). The primary objective of this study was to assess the antipyretic properties of the aqueous and its solvent fractions as well as methanol *T. gillettii* root bark extracts in animal model of fever. The use of the plant's root barks in traditional medicine has been noted for addressing various disease conditions, notably including injury-induced swelling, fever and pains management (Kikweta et al., 2013, Cimanga et al., 2019), and other medicinal plant's parts knew these medical purposes (Akkol et al., 2012, Aremu and Pendota, 2021, Nascimento et al., 2022, Chinwuba et al., 2024).

In this investigation, the potential effects of extracts and solvent fractions from *Triclisia gillettii* root bark was carried out using the toxican Brewer's yeast inducing high temperatures in selected Swiss albino mice. The cutaneous injection of this toxican in mice at dose of 10 mL/kg bw corresponding to 3g/kg bw of 30% w/v Brewer's yeast induced high rectal temperatures from 39.9 ± 0.9 to $40.3 \pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$. Moreover, this study proceeded to monitor the rectal temperatures of treated mice at 1, 3 and 5h following the administration of all test samples including Aspirin as reference antipyretic drugs, extracts and solvent fractions.

Afterwards, the oral administration of Aspirin as reference antipyretic drug at dose of 100 mg/kg bw caused significant lowering of rectal temperature to $37.5 \pm 0.2^{\circ}\text{C}$ in 1h and continued to decrease gradually to attain low value of $34.6 \pm 0.8^{\circ}\text{C}$ after 5h of treatment. The same, the oral administration of aqueous Tgrb-1 and methanol 80% Tgrb-2 extracts at dose of 200 and 400 mg/kg bw reached remarkably reduction of rectal temperatures in dose-dependent manner (Table 1). Administered at high dose of 400 mg/kg bw, aqueous Tgrb-1 and methanol 80% Tgrb-2 extracts brought both the rectal temperatures of treated mice to values of $38.06 \pm 0.6^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $37.5 \pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ in 1h and knew significant decrease until the values of 37.0 ± 0.4 and $36.5 \pm 0.7^{\circ}\text{C}$ found in acceptable physiological limits $36.5-37.5^{\circ}$. An increase of rectal Tgrb-1.1 to 1.4 chloroform, ethylacetate, *n*-butanol and residual aqueous solvent fractions from the partition of aqueous Tgrb-1 extract served at high dose of 400 mg/kg bw, played the same

role by reducing significantly rectal temperatures of treated mice from 36.8 ± 0.5 to $39.06\pm 0.6^\circ\text{C}$ in 1h and

continues to decrease gradually to attain values from 36.5 ± 0.5 to $37.0\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ after 5h of treatment.

Table 1: Rectal temperatures of induced by extracts, solvent fractions and crude polysaccharides on treated mice.

Groups »	Dose	Initial temperatures	1h	3h	5h
TNN. Control I	DW	36.8 ± 0.05	38.1 ± 0.04	37.3 ± 0.06	37.0 ± 0.03
TToxic N. control BY II	DW+Y	37.8 ± 0.8	39.9 ± 0.9	40.0 ± 0.6	40.3 ± 0.5
Aspirin	100	37.5 ± 0.4	37.5 ± 0.2	36.8 ± 0.6	34.6 ± 0.8
Tgrb-1 IV	200	37.4 ± 0.5	37.2 ± 0.5	38.1 ± 0.5	36.7 ± 0.5
	400	37.2 ± 0.4	38.0 ± 0.6	37.4 ± 0.5	37.0 ± 0.4
Tgrb-1.1 VI	200	36.8 ± 0.6	36.8 ± 0.5	38.1 ± 0.4	36.6 ± 0.8
	400	37.2 ± 0.8	37.5 ± 0.4	38.1 ± 0.4	36.8 ± 0.5
Tgrb-1.2 VII	200	36.7 ± 0.4	38.7 ± 0.6	36.7 ± 0.4	37.2 ± 0.4
	400	37.3 ± 0.5	38.2 ± 0.6	37.3 ± 0.6	36.5 ± 0.5
Tgrb-1.3 VIII	200	36.7 ± 0.7	37.7 ± 0.4	37.4 ± 0.4	37.4 ± 0.7
	400	37.4 ± 0.5	39.0 ± 0.6	37.2 ± 0.5	36.8 ± 0.5
Tgrb-1.4 IX	200	37.1 ± 0.5	38.2 ± 0.6	37.3 ± 0.5	37.0 ± 0.7
	400	37.1 ± 0.4	37.3 ± 0.5	38.1 ± 0.2	37.0 ± 0.5
Tgrb-2 IV	200	36.7 ± 0.6	37.5 ± 0.2	37.3 ± 0.7	36.5 ± 0.8
	400	37.5 ± 0.5	37.5 ± 0.5	38.0 ± 0.2	36.5 ± 0.7
Trgb-2.1	200	37.8 ± 0.5	37.6 ± 0.8	37.6 ± 0.07	37.5 ± 0.07
	400	37.6 ± 0.3	37.5 ± 0.0	36.5 ± 0.5	36.4 ± 0.04
Trgb-2.2	200	37.8 ± 0.5	38.4 ± 0.5	37.0 ± 0.6	36.6 ± 0.6
	400	37.5 ± 0.7	37.5 ± 0.3	36.8 ± 0.4	36.5 ± 0.03
Trgb-2.3	200	37.6 ± 0.6	37.5 ± 0.8	37.7 ± 0.13	37.5 ± 0.6
	400	37.8 ± 0.10	37.5 ± 0.12	37.3 ± 0.11	37.3 ± 0.8
Trgb-2.4	200	37.7 ± 0.5	38.0 ± 0.4	37.0 ± 0.4	37.4 ± 0.6
	400	37.4 ± 0.0	37.0 ± 0.6	36.7 ± 0.7	37.1 ± 0.0
CPTgrb X	200	36.6 ± 0.6	37.3 ± 0.8	37.5 ± 0.4	36.7 ± 0.6
	400	37.3 ± 0.4	38.1 ± 0.7	36.7 ± 0.2	36.5 ± 0.8

See Table 1.N. TNN control : test normal negative control, TToxic N. BY : test toxic negative control Brewer's yeast, DW: distilled water, Ac-1 : aqueous extract, Ac-1.1 to 1.4: chloroform, ethylacetate, *n*-butanol and residual aqueous solvent fractions respectively, CPTgrb : crude polysaccharides.

temperature was remarked with aqueous Tgrb-1 extract and seemed to negligible since it landed immediately in normal physiological limit (Tabel 1). At the same manner, Tgrb-2.1 to 2.4 solvent fractions from the partition of methanol 80% Trgb-2 extract managed at the same oral dose as the first solvent fractions, acted also causing significant reduction of rectal temperatures of treated mice to values from 37.0 ± 0.6 to $38.4\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ in 1h and carried on to decrease progressively to values from 36.3 ± 0.03 to $37.3\pm 0.0^\circ\text{C}$ after 5h of treatment. Crude polysaccharides responded the same manner by

decreasing rectal temperatures of treated mice to 38.1 ± 0.7 in 1h and to $36.5\pm 0.8^\circ\text{C}$ after 5h of treatment although an increase was noted without important significance since it landed immediately in normal limits (Table 1). Nevertheless, an increase induced by the oral administration of Tgrb-1.3 administered at 400 mg/kg bw, Tgrb-2.2 and 2.4 solvent fractions served at 200 mg/kg bw, was observed in 1h, but was seemed to be negligible because it landed immediately in normal ranges $36.5\text{-}37.5^\circ\text{C}$ (Table 1).

Figure 3 showed the effects of test normal negative control (TNNc), test toxic negative Brewer's yeast control (TTNCBY) served at 10 ml/kg bw, aqueous Tgrb-1 extract, methanol 80% Tgrb-2 extracts administered at oral dose of 400 mg/kg bw and Aspirin administered at oral dose of 100 mg/kg bw on rectal temperatures induced by the toxican Brewer's yeast in

Swiss albino mice. It revealed that the effects began at 1h at which some samples like TNNc and Tgrb-1 increased rectal temperature low compared to TTNcBY (Fig. 2). These rectal temperatures landed immediately in acceptable physiologic limits after 3 and 5h, and this effect had no significant consequence and appeared negligible since the last recorded temperatures were all found in acceptable physiological limits demonstrating thus, that these test samples exerted well antipyretic activity. In other terms, they significantly declined these

rectal temperatures of treated mice with pyrexia compared to test toxic Brewer’s yeast negative control, evinced that these samples were endorsed with appreciable antipyretic effects and the last temperatures were significant and determinative (Fig. 2). Methanol 80% Tgrb-2 extract exhibited greater activity compared to aqueous Tgrb-1 extract due to the nature of extractive solvent restored methanol 80% as good solvent for the extraction of antipyretic principles in high amount.

Figure 2: Antipyretic effects revealed by test test normal negative control (TNNc), test toxic negative Brewer’s yeast (TTNcBY), aqueous Tgrb-1 extract, methanol 80% Tgrb-2 extract and Aspirin in treated mice with pyrexia.

Chloroform, ethylacetate, *n*-butanol and residual aqueous Tgrb-1.1 to Tgrb-1.4 solvent fractions respectively, administered at doses of 200 and 400 mg/kg bw, caused also significant lowering of rectal temperatures induced by the toxican Brewer’s yeast in dose-dependent manner (Table 1). Indeed, administered at high dose of 400 mg/kg bw, they acted in the same manner as aqueous Tgrb-1 extract, by lowering these rectal temperatures of treated mice to values between 37.3±0.5 and 39.0±0.6°C in 1h and knew significant decrease after 5h by bringing back them to low values ranging between 36.7±0.5 and 37.0±0.5°C. In the same way, oral administration of crude polysaccharide CPTgrb at the same doses reacted in the same manner as extracts and solvent fractions (Table 1). Given orally at high dose of 400 mg/kg bw, it reduced significantly rectal temperatures of treated mice by bringing back their values to 38.1±0.7 in 1h and to low value of 36.5±0.8°C after 5h. In general, it was observed that all samples form methanol Tgrb-2 extract

including the extract its self, exhibited high antipyretic effects compared to dose from aqueous Tgrb-1 extract including the extract its self.

Figure 3 retrieved the effects of test normal negative control (TNNc), test toxic negative Brewers’s yeast (TTNcBY) served at 10 ml/kg bw, chloroform (Tgrb-1.1), ethylacetate (TgRb-1.2, *n*-butanol (Tgrb-1.3), residual aqueous (Tgrb-1.4) solvent fractions administered orally at 400 mg/kg bw and Aspirin given orally at dose of 100 mg/kg bw on rectal temperatures induced by the toxican Brewer’s yeast in Swiss albino mice. Results indicated that after 1h of treatment, some samples such as TNNc, TTNcBY, ethyacetate (Tgrbb-1.2) and *n*-butanol (Tgrb-1.3) solvent fractions provoked an increase of rectal temperatures in 1h and chloroform (tgrb-1.1) and residual aqueous (Tgrb-1.4) solvent fractions in 3h, without no significant consequence.

Figure 3: Antipyretic effects revealed by test test normal negative control (TNNc), test toxic negative Brewer’s yeast (TTNcBY), chloroform (grb-1.1), ethylacetate (Tgrb-1.2), *n*-butanol (Tgrb-1.3) and residual aqueous (Tgrb-1.4) solvent fractions and Aspirin.

Since these temperatures abated or landed quickly in acceptable physiological ranges 36.5-37.5°C in following hours as the last rectal temperature was the most important demonstrating the reductive characteristic of these test samples manifesting thus their antipyretic effects (Fig. 3). Ethylacetate (Tgrb-1.2) and Tgrb-2.2 rich in flavonoid constituents showed high activity confronted to remaining respective chloroform (Tgrb-1.1), *n*-butanol (Tgrb-1.3) and residual aqueous Tgrb-1.4), and chloroform Tgrb-2.1, *n*-butanol (Tgrb-2.3) and residual aqueous Tgrb-2.4) solvents fractions rich in steroids an terpenoids, in saponins and other phenolic compounds than flavonoids.

Figure 4 displayed effects of Tgrb-2.1 to 1.4 and Aspirin on rectal temperatures induced by the toxican Brewer's yeast in treated mice. Results revealed that test normal negative control (TNNc) administered 5 ml distilled water reached rectal temperature from 37.0 to 38.1°C during 1 and 5h of treatment being in acceptable physiological limits 36.5-37.5°C although an increase of this temperature was observed in 1h without significant importance since it landed quickly in normal ranges in the following hours (Fig. 4), while test toxic negative control Brewer's.

Figure 4. Antipyretic effects revealed by test test normal negative control (TNNc), test toxic negative Brewer's yeast (TTNCBY), chloroform (Tgrb-1.1), ethylacetate (Tgrb-1.2), *n*-butanol (Tgrb-1.3) and residual aqueous (Tgrb-1.4) solvent fractions and n.

Yeast caused significant increase of these temperatures (TTNNcBY) from 39.9 to 40.3°C out of normal ranges (Fig. 4). Therefore, tea oral administration of Tgb-2.1 to 2.4 occasioned significant reduction of these temperatures to values from 37.0 to 37.5°C and go on to decrease to low values from 36.3 to 37.3°C while Aspirin used as standard drug produced only 34.6°C under normal limits showing thus, its strong reductor effect.

These lowering effects displayed by Aspirin, extracts and solvent fractions clearly demonstrated that these samples were endorsed with good and interesting antipyretic activity *in vivo*. Nevertheless, it was observed that during the treatment, some samples such as aqueous Tgrb-1 extract, ethylacetate Tgrb-1.2 and *n*-butanol tgrb-1.3 solvent fractions as well crude polysaccharides CPTgrb reached increasing of rectal temperatures at the same test dose without significant importance since they landed immediately in acceptable ranges in following hours (Table 1) and this effects was found to be negligible. This situation was also found in other previous studies on the evaluation of antipyretic activity of other medicinal plants without no comment (Tesema *et al.*, 2015, Adbidoeye *et al.*, Olorukooba *et al.*, 2020, Ghauri *et al.*, 2021, Geresu *et al.*, 2022, Tegegne *et al.*, 2022, Alkandahri *et al.*, 2022, 2024). Our results were in

good agreement with Zhu *et al.*, 2020, Asad *et al.*, 2024, Fu *et al.*, 2024) for the antipyretic effect of crude polysaccharides.

This study proved that Aspirin, aqueous and methanol Tgrb-1 and Tgreb-2 extracts respectively, solvent fractions as well as crude polysaccharides CPTgrb showed antipyretic activity in the toxican Brewer's yeast induced fever in Swiss albino mice. With a dose of 100 and 400 mg/kg bw, significant antipyretic effect was started with Aspirin as reference antipyretic drug, extracts, solvent fractions and crude polysaccharide started at 1h and proceeded to decrease significantly after 5h of treatment (Table 1). Thereafter, the antipyretic effects showed by all test samples, were sustained with both doses in all test samples as also previously reported by Naveen *et al.*, (2019) for the antipyretic activity of *Vitex negundo* and *Andrographis paniculata* leaves in rabbits. The antipyretic effects of test samples from *T. gillettii* root bark were qualitatively comparable to Aspirin used as a standard drug.

Body thermal regulation demanded a careful balance between heat generation and heat loss in the hypothalamus, which centrally maintained the set-point at which body temperature is maintained (Rang *et al.*,

2007, Ain et al? 2023). The elements stated above raise this set-point in fever. Antipyretic medications were known to work either centrally on the brain's temperature control center or peripherally via vasodilation and heat dissipation (Khan et al., 2014, Ain et al., 2023). They reseted the hypothalamic thermostat and lowered fever quickly by increasing heat dissipation (sweating, cutaneous vasodilation) (Ain et al., 2023). They also worked by preventing the production of prostaglandin E₂ (Cheng et al., 2008, Ain et al., 2023). The results indicated all samples from *T. gillettii* root barks had an antipyretic property qualitatively comparable to that of aspirin (standard drug) in Swiss albino mice although PGE₁-induced elevations in body temperature. As a result, inhibition of prostaglandin synthesis could be a plausible mechanism of *T. gillettii* root barks samples antipyretic activity as Aspirin, and there were multiple mediators or processes underlying fever pathogenesis (Aziz et al., 2013, AI et al., 2023). Any of these mediators might be inhibited from producing antipyresis. We concluded from the above study that *T. gillettii* root barks had antipyretic potential against pyrexia model in abino mice as already mentioned above.

Mechanisms actions of some secondary metabolites were previously reported and were summarized in the present study.

Alkaloids acted as antipyretic agents primarily by reducing fever through the inhibition of pro-inflammatory mediators, particularly by blocking cyclooxygenase (COX) enzyme activity and inhibiting prostaglandin E₂ (PGE₂) synthesis in the hypothalamus. They often targeted inflammatory pathways, reduced interleukin-1 (IL - 1) and IL - 6 levels, suppressed nitric oxide (NO) production, and modulated immune cell infiltration.

Key mechanisms of action for antipyretic alkaloids included

- Inhibition of cyclooxygenase (COX-2) and PGE₂: Alkaloids like lycorine inhibited COX-2 and PGE₂ production in macrophages, reducing fever and inflammation.
- Cytokine regulation: Alkaloids such as those in *Alstonia scholaris* and lycorine inhibited the production of inflammatory mediators (e.g., IL - 1, IL - 6) and disrupt signaling pathways like STAT1/STAT3.
- Inhibition of inflammation: Berberine, berbamine, and palmatine had shown significant, dose-dependent antipyretic and anti-inflammatory activity.
- Neurotransmitter modulation: Some alkaloids, such as diterpenoid alkaloids (e.g., aconitine,

lappaconitine), acted via modulation of norepinephrine and serotonin pathways.

- Antiviral-induced fever reduction: Many alkaloids (e.g., lycorine) exhibited anti-coronavirus and antiviral properties, which indirectly reduced fever by preventing viral replication and associated cytokine storms. These compounds often acted as natural alternatives to NSAIDs, targeting similar pathways to reduce elevated body temperature, particularly in infectious, immunological, and neoplastic conditions (Anonymous, 2025b).

Flavonoids acted as antipyretic (fever-reducing) agents primarily by exerting potent anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects, inhibiting key inflammatory pathways and enzymes. They reduced fever by suppressing cyclooxygenase (COX-2) activity, reducing prostaglandin synthesis, and inhibiting pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α . Common antipyretic flavonoids included quercetin, apigenin, and kaempferol.

Their key mechanisms of action were

- Inhibition of Prostaglandin synthesis: Similar to nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), flavonoids like hesperidin and diosmin inhibited cyclooxygenase (COX) and lipoxygenase (LOX) enzymes, crucial for producing pro-inflammatory, fever-inducing mediators.
- Suppression of Pro-inflammatory Cytokines: Flavonoids decreased the expression and released of interleukin-1beta (IL-1 β), interleukin-6 (IL-6), and tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), which were major mediators of fever.
- NF- κ B Pathway Inhibition: Flavonoids (e.g., quercetin) block the nuclear factor kappa-light chain enhancer of activated B cells (NF- κ B) pathway, a master regulator of inflammatory gene expression.
- Antioxidant Activity: Flavonoids scavenged free radicals and reactive oxygen species (ROS), reducing oxidative stress that contributed to inflammation and fever.
- Enzyme Inhibition: They inhibited enzymes involved in inflammation, including phospholipase A₂, which initiates the release of arachidonic acid. These actions helped modulate the body's immune response to pyrogens, thereby lowering elevated temperatures.

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- **Antioxidant Activity:** Flavonoids scavenged free radicals and reactive oxygen species (ROS), reducing oxidative stress that contributed to inflammation and fever.
- **Enzyme Inhibition:** They inhibited enzymes involved in inflammation, including phospholipase A2, which initiates the release of arachidonic acid. These actions helped modulate the body's immune response to pyrogens, thereby lowering elevated temperatures (Anonymous, 2025c).

Steroids (glucocorticoids) acted as potent antipyretic agents primarily by suppressing the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines (like IL-1, IL-6, and TNF- α) and inhibiting the synthesis of prostaglandins (specifically PGE₂) in the hypothalamus. They achieved this by binding to cytosolic receptors, inhibiting phospholipase A2 via lipocortin-1 induction, and repressing genes through NF- κ B and AP-1.

Their key mechanisms of action were

- **Inhibition of Prostaglandin Synthesis:** Steroids induced the synthesis of lipocortin-1 (annexin A1), which inhibited phospholipase A2. This prevented the release of arachidonic acid, the precursor to prostaglandins, thereby reducing PGE₂ levels in the brain, which was responsible for fever generation.
- **Suppression of Pyrogenic Cytokines:** They suppressed the transcription of genes responsible for producing pyrogenic cytokines, including IL-1, IL-6, and TNF- α , which were triggered during inflammation or infection.
- **Genomic Actions via Receptor Binding:** Steroids diffused into cells and bind to intracellular glucocorticoid receptors (GR). This complex translocated to the nucleus to repress pro-inflammatory genes (transrepression) by inhibiting transcription factors like NF- κ B and AP-1.
- **Downregulation of COX-2:** Glucocorticoids reduced the expression of cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-

2), an enzyme crucial for producing fever-inducing prostaglandins.

- **Reduction of CSF IL-6:** Dexamethasone and other glucocorticoids can directly reduce the increased concentrations of interleukin-6 (IL-6) in the cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) (Anonymous, 2025d).

Terpenoids functions as antipyretic (fever-reducing) agents primarily by suppressing the inflammatory processes that led to elevated body temperature. They acted on various pathways within the inflammatory cascade, often reducing the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines, inhibiting key enzymes in prostaglandin synthesis, and acting as antioxidants.

Their key mechanisms of action included

- **Inhibition of Prostaglandin E2 (PGE₂) and COX-2:** Similar to conventional nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), many terpenoids inhibited the enzyme cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2), which reduced the production of PGE₂ in the hypothalamus, the direct mediator of fever.
- **Suppression of pro-inflammatory cytokines:** Terpenoids, such as limonene, myrcene, and camphor inhibited the release of cytokines like Interleukin 1- β (IL-1 β), Interleukin-6 (IL-6), and Tumor Necrosis Factor-alpha (TNF- α).
- **Inhibition of NF- κ B signaling:** Terpenoids inhibited the nuclear factor-kappa B (NF- κ B) pathway, a critical regulator of pro-inflammatory gene expression, thereby reducing the inflammatory response.
- **Modulation of MAPK Pathway:** Some terpenoids reduced the phosphorylation of mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPK), specifically p38, JNK, and ERK, further decreasing the production of inflammatory mediators.
- **Antioxidant Activity:** Terpenoids can reduce reactive oxygen species (ROS), which were known to mediate leukocyte migration and increase vessel permeability during inflammation.
- **Nitric Oxide (NO) Inhibition:** Terpenoids, including those found in *Inula* flowers and *Echinops kebericho*, had been shown to inhibit the production of nitric oxide (NO) induced by inflammatory stimuli.

Common antipyretic terpenoids like

- **Camphor and Borneol:** Known to inhibit pro-inflammatory mediators and reduce fever.
- **Limonene and Myrcene:** Frequently reported to suppress IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α .
- **Costunolide and Lupeol:** Sesquiterpenes found to inhibit PGE₂ and COX-2 expression.
- **Artemisinin:** A sesquiterpene known to act on inflammatory signaling pathways.

These natural compounds offered a potentially safer alternative to synthetic antipyretics, often with lower toxicity. These multi-faceted actions suppressed fever, particularly when it was driven by intense inflammation or immunological responses, rather than simple infectious causes (Anonymous, 2025e).

Polysaccharides, particularly those derived from medicinal plants and fungi, acted as effective antipyretic (fever-reducing) agents through multi-target mechanisms that suppressed inflammatory responses, regulated body metabolism, and modulated the immune system. Their antipyretic action was often achieved by inhibiting fever-induced inflammation, improving the gut-brain axis, and lowering the levels of pyrogenic cytokines and mediators

The key mechanisms of action of polysaccharides antipyretic agents included

- Suppression of Inflammatory Signaling Pathways: Polysaccharides primarily inhibited the TLR4/NF- κ B signaling pathway, which is a core mediator of inflammatory responses. By downregulating this pathway, they reduced the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α , IL-1 β , and IL-6.
- Inhibition of Prostaglandin E2 (PGE2) Production: Similar to conventional NSAIDs, many natural polysaccharides (e.g., *Tetragium hemsleyanum* polysaccharide) reduced the levels of PGE2, a key fever-inducing mediator, in the serum and hypothalamus, thereby directly reducing fever.
- Modulation of the Gut-Brain Axis and Microbiota: Polysaccharides acted as prebiotics to balance the gut microbiota, which improved metabolic profiles and reduced systemic inflammation. They can restore gut barrier function and reduce the release of LPS (lipopolysaccharide) that triggers fever.
- Antioxidant Effects (Nrf2/ARE Pathway): Polysaccharides possessed strong antioxidant activities, largely by activating the Nrf2/ARE pathway, which regulated downstream antioxidant enzymes to reduce oxidative stress-induced tissue damage.
- Metabolic Reprogramming: Polysaccharides helped normalize the high metabolic state associated with fever by influencing lipid, amino acid, and energy metabolism.
- Inhibition of pyroptosis: Some polysaccharides (e.g., from *Tetragium hemsleyanum*) had been shown to inhibit NLRP3-Caspase-1-Gasdermin D (GSDMD) signaling, thereby blocking macrophage pyroptosis (inflammatory cell death) and reducing IL-1 β secretion.
- Structure-activity relationships.
- Molecular Weight: Lower molecular weight polysaccharides often exhibited stronger immune-stimulating and anti-inflammatory effects due to better cell membrane penetration.
- Sulfation: The introduction of sulfate groups to polysaccharides can significantly increase their anti-inflammatory, antiviral, and antioxidant activities.
- Structure Type: Branched polysaccharides, such as β -D-(1 \rightarrow 3)-glucans, often had higher immunomodulatory activity compared to linear ones.
- Examples of polysaccharides with mechanism of action:
 - *Tetragium hemsleyanum* polysaccharide (THP): Reduced body temperature by decreasing thermoregulatory mediators, lowering proinflammatory cytokines, and inhibiting the TLR4/NF- κ B pathway.
 - *Bile Arisaema* polysaccharide (BAP): Exerted strong antipyretic effects by balancing gut microbiota, regulating lipid/amino acid metabolism, and suppressing the NF- κ B/TLR4/MyD88 pathway.
 - Sulfated Polysaccharides: Acted as anti-inflammatory agents to reduce NO production, TNF- α , and IL-6 levels in macrophage models (anonymous, 2025f).

Tannins acted as antipyretic (fever-reducing) agents primarily by inhibiting the inflammatory processes that trigger fever and by modulating immune responses. Their mechanisms of action were closely linked to their potent antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, which allow them to interfere with the signaling pathways that led to increased body temperature.

Key mechanisms of action

- Inhibition of Pro-inflammatory Mediators: Tannins, particularly hydrolyzable tannins, reduce the production of inflammatory mediators like prostaglandin E2 (PGE₂) and nitric oxide (NO). These compounds are key, fever-inducing mediators in the hypothalamus.
- Cyclooxygenase (COX) Inhibition: Similar to synthetic NSAIDs, tannins can inhibit the COX-2 enzyme, preventing the conversion of arachidonic acid to fever-inducing prostaglandins.
- Downregulation of Cytokines: Tannins reduced the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α , IL-1 β , and IL-6.
- NF- κ B Signaling Pathway Inhibition: Tannins inhibited the Nuclear Factor-kappa B (NF- κ B) signaling pathway, a master regulator of inflammation, which reduces the overall inflammatory response.
- Antioxidant Activity: By acting as free radical scavengers, tannins reduced oxidative stress, which was often associated with the inflammation that caused fever.
- Modulation of Immune Responses: Tannins can enhance the functionality of macrophages and

modulated the secretion of cytokines, aiding in the resolution of the inflammation that produced fever.

- Types of tannins and their Effects
- Hydrolyzable Tannins (e.g., tannic acid, ellagitannins): These were particularly effective at inhibiting acid secretion and reducing inflammatory cytokine production.
- Condensed Tannins (Proanthocyanidins): These were known for their potent ROS (Reactive Oxygen Species) reduction, anti-inflammatory activity, and ability to inhibit lipid peroxidation.

Indirect mechanism

Tannins can form a protective, astringent layer on mucous membranes, which might reduce the absorption of toxins and antigens that trigger immune responses and fever. In summary, the antipyretic effect of tannins is primarily due to their ability to act as anti-inflammatory agents that inhibited the key, fever-inducing mediators (PGE_2), cytokines) and enzymes (COX-2) in the body (Anonymous, 2025g).

Brewer's yeast was used to induce fever in Swiss albino mice for 5h. Its subcutaneous injection led to induce pyrexia or fever by increasing the synthesis of prostaglandins with consequence the increase of body temperature. It was considered as a useful test for screening plant extracts and solvent fractions as well as various synthetic drugs for the assessment their potential antipyretic activity in animal model. The inhibition of prostaglandins synthesis was the possible mechanism as that of Paracetamol and this effect can be achieved by blocking the cyclooxygenase enzyme activity as reported by Rajendar *et al.*, (2025) for ethanol root extract of *Bahonia racemosa* in animal model.

Results from the present investigation revealed that aqueous and its chloroform, ethylacetate, *n*-butanol and residual aqueous solvent fractions as well as methanol 80% were able to significantly decline high rectal temperatures induced by the toxic Brewer's yeast in treated mice at oral dose of 200 and 400 mg/kg bodyweight comparable to aspirin used at oral dose of 100 mg/kg body weight. This significant lowering of rectal temperatures showed by these analyzed samples clearly demonstrated that they were endowed with appreciable antipyretic effects mainly exploitable in traditional medicine in favor of aqueous extract employed to treat human fever.

4. CONCLUSION

This study reported for the first time the antipyretic effects of aqueous and its chloroform, ethylacetate, *n*-butanol and residual aqueous solvent fractions as well as methanol 80% extracts from *Triglisia gillettii* root barks. Results revealed that all samples exhibited interesting and appreciable antipyretic activity in animal model expressed with different magnitudes. It could validate the beneficial effects of *T. gillettii* root barks in traditional medicine, support and justify the traditional use of

mainly aqueous extract for the treating of fever in DR Congo without forgotten other African countries where it knew the same medical purpose. Next studies were planned aiming the isolation of active antipyretic principles mainly alkaloids without forgotten other phytochemical groups.

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